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***CURE KINETICS AND SHRINKAGE
MEASUREMENTS IN A FAST CURING
EPOXY AMINE RESIN SYSTEM***

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RESIDUAL STRESS

“Residual stresses can be defined as stress fields that exist in the absence of any external loads” – developed during the manufacturing state

Microscopic

- Stress between fibre and matrix at individual ply

Macroscopic

- Ply to Ply difference due to anisotropy in CTE or chemical shrinkage

Structural

- Variation in shrinkage thru the thickness

Why is it important in CFRP

- Decreases strength
- Dimensional inaccuracies
- Could lead to premature failure especially during cyclic loadings

FACTORS INFLUENCING RESIDUAL STRESS IN CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES

PROCESS/CONSTITUTIVE MODELS

MODELLING RESIDUAL STRESS

CURE KINETIC MODELS

Model	Expression
Springer-Loos	$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = (K_1 + K_2\alpha)(1 - \alpha)(B - \alpha)$
Cole with diffusion	$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \frac{1}{1 + e^{C(\alpha - \alpha_{C0} + \alpha_C T)}} K_1 \alpha^m (1 - \alpha)^n$
Kamal	$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = (K_1 + K_2 \alpha^m) (1 - \alpha)^n$
White and hann	$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = K_1 \alpha^m (1 - \alpha)^n$
Kamal with diffusion	$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \frac{1}{1 + e^{C(\alpha - \alpha_C)}} (K_1 + K_2 \alpha^m) (1 - \alpha)^n$

Parameter	Expression
$K_i = A_i e^{\frac{\Delta E_i}{RT}}$	Arrhenius factor
α	Resin (or composite) DOC
T	Absolute temperature
ΔE_i	Activation energy
A_i	Pre-Exponential factor
C	Diffusion Constant

ISOTHERMAL AND RATE OF REACTION

- Resin - mixture of Isopropylidenediphenol – epichlorohydrin copolymer and propanetriol glycidyl ether.
- Hardener - 4,4'-methylenebis[2-methyl-Cyclohexanamine].
- Isothermal runs were conducted on a Netzsch DSC Polyma 214 at a heating rate of 100C/min.

MODEL FITTING USING KAMAL SOURER

- Model fitting was conducted using matlab
- Excellent fit was obtained using the kamal sourer model

KINETIC PARAMETERS

MODEL WITHOUT DIFFUSION

- Euler method was used to numerically solve the equation to obtain conversion
- Very good fit is obtained up to a certain Conversion
- Deviation at higher conversion is due to the changeover from kinetic control to diffusion control.

MODEL WITH DIFFUSION

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \frac{1}{1+e^{c(\alpha-\alpha_c)}} (K_1+K_2\alpha^m)(1-\alpha)^n$$

Diffusion factor

- Optimization parameter
- Chern and Poehlein to improve the cure kinetics model for higher degree of cure values

CTE MEASUREMENTS

- ❑ CTE measurements were conducted using a TMA Q400
- ❑ Samples of 5 x 5 (d x h) were obtained at different degrees of cure
- ❑ The samples were subjected to ramp from room temperature to 250C.
- ❑ The slope of the dimensional change curve was recorded as the CTE.

Resin	Degree of Cure (%)	CTE $\mu\text{m}/(\text{m}^\circ\text{C})$
	75	144.9
	85	154.5

SHRINKAGE LITERATURE

GRAVIMETRIC TECHNIQUE

- Change of density at isothermal temperature

$$\left(\frac{\Delta V}{V}\right)_{\text{shrinkage}, T_c} = \frac{\Delta G_{T_c}}{\rho_{f, T_f} \times V_{r, T_c}}$$

$$V_{\text{uncured}, T_c} = \frac{m_{r, T_0}}{\rho_{r, T_0}} \times [1 + 3 \times \alpha_1 (T_c - T_0)]$$

$$\rho_{f, T_c} = \frac{\rho_{f, T_0}}{1 + \gamma_f (T_f - T_0)}$$

- Bi-linear relationship
- Estimate ~ 11% shrinkage

DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION

GOM ARAMIS

GOM ATOS

SUMMARY

- Cure kinetics was modelled using the Kamal souer model considering diffusion controlled mechanism.
- Thermo-physical properties were determined and aided in modelling.
- Cure shrinkage models were developed.
- Non contact strain measurement using GOM Aramis was correlated with the shrinkage model.
- Inputs to FEA model were created for the studied resin system.